

Notes on the grass orb-web spider *Neoscona moreli* (Vinson, 1863) from South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae)

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Abstract: *Neoscona moreli* (Vinson, 1863) is an African endemic species that was introduced to Cuba and Argentina. Information on their behaviour, general morphology and distribution in South Africa with photographs on their webs and lifestyle are provided.

Key words: Free State; South African National Survey of Arachnida; web building

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Neoscona* is represented by 116 species (World Spider Catalog, 2022) and 17 species are recorded from South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022). Large numbers of *Neoscona* specimens were sampled during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa). One of these species, *Neoscona moreli* (Vinson, 1863), is commonly found making orb-webs in grass and can be recognised by the abdominal pattern and slightly elongated abdomen (Fig.1). The species was originally described as *Epeira morelii* from Reunion. It is a species with a wide distribution known from the Afrotropical Region as well as from Cuba to Argentina (Grasshoff, 1980).

Neoscona moreli are very colourful spiders and were sampled from several localities in South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2022). In this paper, we provide information on the distribution of *N. moreli* with observations and photographs taken in the field over a period of several years.

METHOD

The voucher specimens sampled during SANSa surveys over a period of 20 years are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). Observation on their behaviour was carried out in grassland at the Mpetsane Conservancy Estate (MCE), which is situated in the Eastern Free State highlands some 14 km from Clocolan. The MCE (28°48'S; 27°39'E) covers 164 ha and is a registered conservancy (Amohela-ho-Spitskop) sanctuary and nature reserve. The first author (AJ), while staying on the estate, is able to regularly walk in the estate to photograph spiders and make observations (Jones & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2021).

TAXONOMY

Neoscona moreli (Vinson, 1863)

Epeira morelii Vinson, 1863: 166, 309

Neoscona moreli Grasshoff, 1980: 407 (removed mf from Synonymy of *N. theisi*); 1986: 56; Dippenaar-Schoeman & Van den Berg 2010: 25; 2014: 62.

For more, see World Spider Catalog: <https://wsc.nmbe.ch/species/4898>

Diagnostic characteristics: Size TL: male 6–8 mm; female 8–16 mm. Female: carapace elongate, slightly longer than wide, narrower in eye region; fawn with brown median band and two lateral bands (Fig. 1); covered with white setae; eyes eight in two rows (4:4). Abdomen elongate-oval, overhanging the carapace; with distinct longitudinal bands; broad median white band bordered by scalloped darker bands, followed by white band (Figs 1, 3 & 9); sides mottled. Ventrally abdomen with dark median band bordered by six white markings; posterior pair smallest (Figs 4 & 10).

Figures 1–2. *Neoscona moreli* 1. Immature male. 2. Female in orb-web. Photo credits: Allen Jones.

Figures 3–8. *Neoscona moreli* 3. Abdomen dorsal view. 4. Abdomen ventral view. 5. Epigyne drawing. 6. Epigyne. 7. Leg II. 8. Tibiae 1–11.3–5,8 After Grasshoff (1986). 6 & 7 Peter Webb

Legs of medium length, with strong setae; kept close to the body when at rest; fawn with distinct bands and spots (Figs 9–11). In male tibiae I with strong setae; tibiae II with dense short dense setae prolaterally (Figs 7–8). Female epigyne with long scapus (Figs 5–6).

Neoscona moreli can be confused with other grass orb-web spiders such as *Kilima decens* and *Larinia* species that are also straw-coloured with bands on their abdomen.

HABITAT

The species is a very common grassland species that was sampled from the Forest, Grassland, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Nama Karoo, Savanna and Thicket Biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011; Haddad *et al.*, 2013). The species was also sampled from avocado (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2005), pecans and pistachio orchards (Haddad *et al.*, 2005), and cotton (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1999), lucerne, maize and tomato fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

BEHAVIOUR

Neoscona moreli are common inhabitants of grasses where they construct orb-webs in low vegetation between the grasses (Figs 13–14). They are found in the field from September to May. Spiderlings hatch in January to February and when still very small, just a few mm in size and they built their own webs. They grow quickly when a regular food supply is available. They catch midges and small flies. By the end of March they are full size already. They usually construct their webs at sunset in the evening, (Fig. 2) and dismantle them the following morning. They are procryptic by day, resting with their bodies appressed to vegetation where they blend in with their elongated, straw-coloured bodies (Figs 1 & 12). They are gregarious and sometimes present in large numbers.

Figures 9–14. *Neoscona moreli*: 9. Female dorsal view. 10. Female ventral view. 11–12. Male. 13. Orb-web in grass. 14. Female in web. Photo credits: Allen Jones.

Some specimens sometimes do remain in the web also during the day and catch flies (Fig. 15). The webs are about 200 mm in diameter and made about 300 mm above ground level. The web consists of a bridge line attached to grasses. The number of radii varies from 21 to 31 and a circular area is made of adhesive threads. They feed on moths (Fig. 17), beetles (Fig. 16), flies (Fig. 18) and grasshoppers (Fig. 19). Males very similar to female and make their own webs (Fig. 11).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Widespread throughout Africa. Introduced to the Caribbean, Colombia, Venezuela to Argentina.

Global distribution after Grasshoff (1980).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Eastern Cape: East London (-33.01, 27.9); Fort Brown Kudu Reserve (-33.13, 26.62); Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); Fort Grey Nature Reserve (-33.19, 27.12); Mkambati Nature Reserve (-31.32, 29.97); Port Alfred (-33.58, 26.89); Port Elizabeth (Pineapple Research Station) (-33.01, 27.9); Kei River Mouth (-32.68, 28.37). **Free State:** Clarens (Farm Adullam) (-28.51, 28.43); Clocolan (Mpetsane Conservation Estate) (-28.92, 27.58); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.5, 26.8); Fouriesburg (Mooifontein) (-28.61, 28.23); Golden Gate Nature Reserve (-28.5, 28.62); Ventersburg (-28.08, 27.14); Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22). **Gauteng:** Bon Accord (-25.62, 28.2); Bronkhorstspuit (Farm Onverwacht) (-25.8, 28.74); Centurion (Irene) (-25.85, 28.16); Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.8, 28.77); Johannesburg (-26.2, 28.04); Kempton Park (-26.09, 28.23); Modderfontein (-26.08, 28.17); Moloto (-25.46, 28.63); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Pretoria/Tshwane (Rietondale Research Station) (-25.73, 28.23); Roodeplaat Dam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Roodeplaat Research Station (-25.66, 28.35); Van Riebeeck Nature Reserve (25.85, 28.16); Irene Gem Village Field (-25.85, 28.16); Dinokeng (-25.4, 28.38); Heidelberg (-26.5, 28.36). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88); Giant's Castle Nature Reserve (-29.23, 29.48); Giant's Cup Wilderness Reserve (Farm Goschen) (-29.97, 29.46); Hluhluwe (-28.02, 32.28); Loteni Nature Reserve (-29.47, 29.52); Ngoye Forest (-28.88, 31.38); Pietermaritzburg (-29.6, 30.38); Pongola (Farm Vergeval) (-27.35, 31.61); Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.4, 32.76); Kamberg Nature Reserve, Fernwood Field Centre (-29.39, 29.67). **Limpopo:** Hoedspruit (-24.34, 30.93); Meetsa-A-Bophelo Mission Station (-24.25, 30.45); Makalali Nature Reserve (-24.34, 30.93);

Figures 15–19. *Neoscona moreli*: 15. Female in orb-web covered with dew early in the morning. 16. Female feeding on a beetle. 17. Feeding on a moth. 18. Feeding on a fly. 19 Feeding on a grasshopper. Photo credits: Allen Jones.

Mosdene Nature Reserve (-24.52, 28.7); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47). **Mpumalanga:** Bourke's Luck (-25.09, 30.46); Brondal (-25.35, 30.84); Delmas (Farm Rietvallei) (26.08, 28.57); Dullstroom (-25.42, 30.1); Graskop (-24.93, 30.84); Groblersdal (-25.16, 29.39); Hendrina (-26.15, 29.71); ; Kruger National Park (Skukuza) (-25.00, 31.97); Loskop Dam Nature Reserve (-25.46, 29.23); Marble Hall (-24.96, 29.29); Middelburg (-25.76, 29.46). **North West:** Barberspan (-26.62, 25.58); Borakalalo Game Reserve (-25.14, 27.82); Kroondal (-75, 27.32); Kgawane Nature Reserve (-25.72, 27.18). **Northern Cape:** Noup (-30.13, 17.2). **Western Cape:** Karoo National Park(-32.28, 22.46).

CONSERVATION

There are no known threats to the species. In South Africa it was sampled from the following protected areas: Roodeplaat Dam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1989); Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1999); Makelali Nature Reserve (Whitmore *et al.*, 2001); Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar *et al.*, 2008); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2009); Mkambati Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2011); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (Fourie *et al.*, 2013) and Mpetsane Conservation Estate (Jones & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2022).

REFERENCES

- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2014. *Field Guide of the Spiders of South Africa*. Lapa Publishers. 424 pp.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2022. *The Araneidae of South Africa*. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide version 2: 3 vol: 150 pp.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LYLE R., LOTZ L.N. & MARAIS P. 2015. South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa): Review of current knowledge, constraints and future needs for documenting spider diversity (Arachnida: Araneae). *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 70: 245–275.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HAMER M. & HADDAD C.R. 2011. Spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) of the vegetation layer of the Mkambati Nature Reserve, Eastern Cape, South Africa. *Koedoe* 53 (#1058): 1–10.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., LEROY A., DE JAGER M. & VAN DEN BERG A. 1999. A check list of the spider fauna of the Karoo National Park, South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae). *Koedoe* 42: 31–42.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN DEN BERG A. & PRENDINI, L. 2009. A checklist of spiders and scorpions of the Nylsvley Nature Reserve, South Africa. *Koedoe* 50: 1–9.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & VAN DEN BERG A.M. 2010. *Spiders of the Kalahari*. Plant Protection Handbook no 18, Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria. 120 pp.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN DEN BERG A.M., HADDAD C.R. & LYLE R. 2013. Spiders in South African agroecosystems: A review (Arachnida, Araneae). *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 68: 57–74.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN DEN BERG A.M. & VAN DEN BERG A. 1989. Species composition and relative seasonal abundance of spiders from the field and tree layers of the Roodeplaat Dam Nature Reserve. *Koedoe* 32: 51–60.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN DEN BERG A.M. & VAN DEN BERG A. 1999. Spiders in South African cotton fields: species diversity and abundance (Arachnida: Araneae). *African Plant Protection* 5: 93–103.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN DEN BERG A.M., VAN DEN BERG A., VAN DEN BERG M.A. & FOORD, S.H. 2005. Spiders in avocado orchards in the Mpumalanga Lowveld of South Africa: Species diversity and abundance (Arachnida: Araneae). *African Plant Protection* 11: 8–16.
- DIPPENAAR S.M., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., MODIBA M.A. & KHOZA T.T. 2008. A checklist of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Polokwane Nature Reserve, Limpopo Province, South Africa. *Koedoe* 50: 10–17.
- FOORD S.H., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & HADDAD C.R. 2011. The faunistic diversity of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Savanna Biome in South Africa. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 66: 170–201.
- FOURIE R., HADDAD C.R., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & GROBLER A. 2013. Ecology of the plant-dwelling spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) of the Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve, South Africa. *Koedoe* 55(#1113): 1–9.
- GRASSHOFF M. 1980. Araneidae-Archiopinae, Araneidae-Araneidae. Contribution a l'etude de la faune terrestre des lies granitiques de l'archipel des Sechelles. *Revue de Zoologie Africaine* 94(2): 387–409.
- GRASSHOFF M. 1986. Die Radnetzspinnen-Gattung *Neoscona* in Afrika (Arachnida: Araneae). *Annales-Musee Royal de l'Afrique Centrale (Sciences Zoologiques)* 250: 1–123.
- HADDAD C.R., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., FOORD S.H., LOTZ L.N. & LYLE R. 2013. The faunistic diversity of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Grassland Biome in South Africa. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 68 (2): 97–122.
- HADDAD C.R., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & PEKAR S. 2005. Arboreal spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) in pistachio orchards in South Africa. *African Plant Protection* 11: 32–41.
- JONES A. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2021. Notes on the orb-weaver spiders of Mpetsane Conservancy Estate in the Free State (Arachnida: Araneae) part 2. *SANSa Newsletter* 39: 14–18.
- VINSON A. 1863. *Aranéides des îles de la Réunion, Maurice et Madagascar*. Paris, i-cxx: 1–337.
- WHITMORE C., SLOTOW R., CROUCH T.E. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2001. Checklist of spiders (Araneae) from savanna ecosystem, Northern Province, South Africa: Including a new family record. *Durban Museum Novitates* 26: 10–19.
- WORLD SPIDER CATALOG. 2022. World Spider Catalog. Version 23.0. Natural History Museum Bern, online at <http://wsc.nmbe.ch>, accessed on 7 April 2022. doi: 10.24436/2